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EVALUATION OF THE IMPACT OF EXCHANGE RATES FLUCTUATIONS ON THE STOCK MARKET WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO NSE.

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ABSTRACT

This Research analyzes the relationship between Nifty returns and Indian rupee-US Dollar Exchange Rates. Several statistical tests have been applied in order to study the behavior and dynamics of both the series. The paper also investigates the impact of both the time series on each other. The period for the study has been taken from December 2011 to August 2014 using daily closing indices.

This Research uses the regression analysis technique to analyze the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on the share prices of NSE. Using the Share prices of the MNCs as dependent variable and the exchange rate fluctuations as an independent variable the regression analysis is done to determine the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on share prices. About 2,800 companies, with a global market capitalization of about \$18 trillion, are listed on the NSE. The results show that a relationship exists between the two variables exchange rates and share prices.

Key Words: Exchange rates, NSE ,

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Stock market return is one of the most relevant and most important metric for the management and the shareholders of the organizations. The study on the factors that impact the share prices is flocking the research databases mostly because the theorist and the applicants want to optimize the management processes and thus provide a guaranteed and stabilized performance of the stock. One factor that impacts the return on stocks and the interest of investors in the stock is the foreign exchange rate.

Foreign exchange return is also important in the context of macroeconomic management of a country meaning to say that if a relationship between the foreign exchange rate and the stock market return is found to exist, then the government has the opportunity to manage the exchange rate and thus the return on the stock

market. Moreover, through the establishment of this relationship, the investors will be able to get another element of predictability in the fluctuations of stock market returns

1.1 EXCHANGE RATE

In finance, an exchange rate between two currencies is the rate at which one currency will be exchanged for another. It is also regarded as the value of one country's currency in terms of another currency. Exchange rates are determined in the foreign exchange market, which is open to a wide range of different types of buyers and sellers where currency trading is continuous.

1.2 EXCHANGE-RATE REGIME

An exchange-rate regime is the way an authority manages its currency in relation to other currencies and the foreign exchange market. It is closely related to monetary policy and the two are generally dependent on many of the same factors.

The basic types are a floating exchange rate, where the market dictates movements in the exchange rate; a pegged float, where a central bank keeps the rate from deviating too far from a target band or value; and a fixed

exchange rate, which ties the currency to another currency, mostly more widespread currencies such as the U.S. dollar or the euro or a basket of currencies.

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Although theories suggest causal relations between stock prices and exchange rates, existing evidence on a micro level provides mixed results. Jorion (1990, 1991), Bodnar and Gentry (1993), and Bartov and Bodnar (1994) all fail to find a significant relation between simultaneous dollar movements and stock returns for U.S. firms. He and Ng (1998) find that only about 25 percent of their sample of 171 Japanese multinationals has significant exchange rate exposure on stock returns.

Griffin and Stulz's (2001) empirical results show that weekly exchange rate shocks have a negligible impact on the value of industry indexes across the world. However, Chamberlain, Howe, and Popper (1997) find that the U.S. banking stock returns are very sensitive to exchange rate movements, but

The liberalization of foreign capital controls and adoption of floating exchange rate regime in South Asian countries have widened the scope of studying the relationship between exchange rates and stock prices. Liberalization of foreign capital controls has opened the possibility of international investment and the adoption of floating exchange rate regime has increased the volatility of foreign exchange market. Thus detecting the association between stock prices and exchange rates has become crucial for the academicians, practitioners and policy makers.

There are different economic models regarding exchange rate determination. "Flow oriented" models introduce country's current account as important determinant of exchange rate. In this perspective, asset markets determine the exchange rate at a point in time, but the current account through its effect on net asset positions, and on asset markets, determine the path of the exchange rates over time (Dornbusch and Fischer, 1980). Thus movements in the stock prices may affect the exchange rates. On the other hand, models that concentrate on the capital account of the balance of payments are known as stock models. Stock models are divided in to monetary models and asset (or portfolio) models.

According to monetary model the exchange rate is seen as a relative asset price. The present value of an asset is thought to be largely influenced by its expected rate of return. Thus actual exchange rate has to be determined by expected future exchange rates (see Gavin, (1989)). Portfolio balance model states that if prices of domestic stock rise, it will persuade investors to buy more domestic assets by selling foreign assets to obtain domestic currency. Increase in demand of domestic currency will lead to appreciation of domestic currency. On the other side, if the prices of domestic asset rise that will result in growth of wealth, which will also increase the demand for money by the investors, That will give rise in domestic interest rates. More foreign capital will be attracted in this situation which will increase the foreign demand for domestic currency and ultimate result will be the appreciation of domestic currency. Thus according to portfolio balance model there is an inverse relationship between stock prices and exchange rates (for detail see, Frenkel (1976), Branson (1983), Macdonald and Taylor (1992)). So there is no theoretical harmony among the models regarding the interactions between stock prices and exchange rates.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 INTRODUCTION

The present study is directed towards studying the dynamics between stock returns volatility and exchange rates movement. We focus our study towards Nifty returns and Indian Rupee-US Dollar Exchange Rates. The period for the study has been taken from December 2011 to August 2014 using daily closing indices.

3.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the impact of the exchange rate fluctuations on the share prices

- To study the nature of the response to specific events national and international
- To study the sensitivity of various industry groups to the fluctuation in exchange rates.
- To find out the impact of exchange rate fluctuations at micro level by studying how the share prices of individual companies respond to exchange rate fluctuations

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study demanded a clear understanding of

- The various exchange rate systems /mechanism and the supporting theories
- The functioning of the US stock market and factors effecting it
- The major policy changes and the changes in the regulatory framework governing the operations of stock markets in USA

And tracking down the following, for the study period between December 2011 to August 2014

- The daily movement of the exchange rate of US Dollar
- The major events affecting NSE stock market
- The daily movement of various indices and share prices

DATA USED

The daily exchange rate fluctuations of the US Dollar during December 2011 to August 2014 and movements in the share prices were brought within the scope of the study. The data analyzes were carried out in the dimensions stated below:

- NSE Composite Index and exchange rate for the entire period 2011-2014
- The share prices of selected companies during 2011-2014

RESEARCH TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

Tools and techniques used consisted of simple graphical analysis, regression

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS & INTREPRETATION

Following table provides the data regarding the top seven Indian companies traded in the New York Stock Exchange and the details about their respective industry as of August 2014:

TABLE-1: the top seven Indian companies traded in the New York Stock

SLNO.	COMPANY	STOCK	EXCHANGE	MARKET CAPITALISATION	INDUSTRY
1	Dr. Reddy's Laboratories	RDY	NSE	8.78B	Pharmacy & Biotech
2	HDFC	HDB	NSE	230.60B	Bank
3	ICICI	IBN	NSE	30.79B	Bank
4	Infosys	INFY	NSE	34.01B	Software & Computer services

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TABLE-2 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDEKS AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR HDFC BANK

SHARE PRICES	EXCHANGE RATES
33.18	61.53
36.25	62.59
30.78	65.71
28.98	60.75
32.9	59.49
36.24	56.58
39.92	53.71
42.1	54.29
37.12	54.35
37.75	53.26
39.9	54.89
40.39	54.25
41.78	53.85
37.09	52.85
37.28	55.52
33.31	55.55
33.64	55.67
32.34	56.09
27.52	52.68
33.78	50.55
33.56	50.58
33.8	49.53
30.54	53.05
25.86	52.41
27.22	49.28
31.16	49.34
28.69	45.88
32.83	44.19
34.21	44.46
34.72	44.99
32.05	44.25
33.64	44.44
33.22	45.17
28.75	45.48
28.23	44.67

GRAPH-1 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDEKS AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR HDFC BANK

TABLE-3 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDES AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR Dr.REDDY’s LABAORATOIRES

SHARE PRICES	EXCHANGE RATES
40.47	61.53
39.38	62.59
37.53	65.71
33.04	60.75
37.02	59.49
37.3	56.58
36.46	53.71
37.36	54.29
31.9	54.35
32.15	53.26
35.45	54.89
32.83	54.25
33.08	53.85
32.09	52.85
30.44	55.52
29.63	55.55
28.62	55.67
29.27	56.09
28.79	52.68
33.09	50.55
33.81	50.58
32.87	49.53
33.41	53.05
28.79	52.41
29.39	49.28
32.43	49.34
29.15	45.88
32.13	44.19
34.88	44.46
33.58	44.99

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34.56	44.25
37.4	44.44
35.55	45.17
32.45	45.48
34.06	44.67

GRAPH-2 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDES AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR Dr.REDDY's LABAORATOIRES

TABLE-4 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDES AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR ICICI BANK

SHARE PRICES	EXCHANGE RATES
35.31	61.53
36.75	62.59
30.01	65.71
25.62	60.75
32.28	59.49
37.66	56.58
44.28	53.71
45.38	54.29
41.58	54.35
40.63	53.26

44.39	54.89
42.27	54.25
39.73	53.85
38.04	52.85
38.9	55.52
31.53	55.55
33.55	55.67
31.41	56.09
27.28	52.68
32.17	50.55
33.1	50.58
34.45	49.53
34.37	53.05
25.09	52.41
27.63	49.28
35.27	49.34
32.95	45.88
37.36	44.19
44.2	44.46
46.79	44.99
44.67	44.25
47.21	44.44
46.67	45.17
40.61	45.48
40.59	44.67

GRAPH-3 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDEKS AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR ICIC BANK

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TABLE-5 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDECS AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR INFOSYS

CHANGE IN SHARE PRICES	CHANGE IN EXCHANGE RATES
53.31	61.53
52.37	62.59
47.2	65.71
45.5	60.75
48.74	59.49
40.41	56.58
40.96	53.71
40.47	54.29
52.27	54.35
52.29	53.26
51.12	54.89
41.02	54.25
43.1	53.85
42.1	52.85
46.76	55.52
40.97	55.55
38.13	55.67
43.41	56.09
40.56	52.68
44.91	50.55
54.15	50.58
54.77	49.53
52.22	53.05
48.79	52.41
49.02	49.28
55.64	49.34
48.23	45.88
48.75	44.19
58.76	44.46

61.6	44.99
58.32	44.25
61.12	44.44
67.23	45.17
62.54	45.48
63.49	44.67

GRAPH-4 SHOWING THE NSE COMPOSITE INDEES AND DOLLAR RATE FLUCTUATIONS FOR INFOSYS

4.2 REGRESSION:

A statistical measure that attempts to determine the strength of the relationship between one dependent variable (usually denoted by Y) and a series of other changing variables (known as independent variables).

The two basic types of regression are linear and multiple regression. Linear regression uses one independent variable to explain and/or predict the outcome of Y, while multiple regressions use two or more independent variables to predict the outcome.

The general form of each type of regression is:

Linear regression: $Y = a + bX + u$

Multiple regression: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_tX_t + u$

Where:

Y= the variable we are trying to predict

X= the variable that we are using to predict Y

A= the intercept

B= the slope

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U= the regression residual

The regression analysis for the data given has been performed by taking the

- Share prices of the individual companies (Dependent Variable) and
- The exchange rates of US Dollar to INR from the period December 2011 to August 2014(Independent variable)

The regression analysis of the top 5 Indian MNCs listed in the NSE is explained in detailed.

DR REDDY LABORATORIES

REGRESSION

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
share prices	33.438857	3.1368378	45
exchange rates	52.339429	5.7382637	45

Correlations

		share prices	exchange rates
Pearson Correlation	share prices	1.000	.267
	exchange rates	.267	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	share prices	.	.061
	exchange rates	.061	.
N	share prices	45	45
	exchange rates	45	45

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	exchange rates ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.267 ^a	.071	.043	3.0687271

a. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.788	1	23.788	2.526	.020 ^b
	Residual	310.764	43	9.417		
	Total	334.552	44			

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

COEFFICIENTS^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	25.810	4.828		5.346	.000
	exchange rates	.146	.092	.267	1.589	.020

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

From B in the fifth table, since the p-value is 0.020, the relationship between exchange rates and share prices is significant. From A in the fourth table, the correlation coefficient, R, is 0.267. Therefore, we can conclude that exchange rates are positively correlated with share prices and the relationship is very strong (R is positive and is much closer to 1). From C in the last table, we can conclude that on average, for every fluctuation in the exchange rates, the share prices of Dr.Reddy’s Laboratories Company vary by a value of .146.

HDFC BANK

REGRESSION: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
share prices	33.735143	4.1988397	45
exchange rates	52.339429	5.7382637	45

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Correlations

		share prices	exchange rates
Pearson Correlation	share prices	1.000	.212
	exchange rates	.212	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	share prices	.	.110
	exchange rates	.110	.
N	share prices	45	45
	exchange rates	45	45

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	exchange rates ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.212 ^a	.045	.016	4.1647141

a. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.049	1	27.049	1.559	.221 ^b
	Residual	572.380	43	17.345		
	Total	599.429	44			

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	25.600	6.553		3.907	.000
exchange rates	.155	.124	.212	1.249	.221

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

From B in the fifth table, since the p-value is 0.221, the relationship between exchange rates and share prices is significant. From A in the fourth table, the correlation coefficient, R, is 0.212. Therefore, we can conclude that exchange rates are positively correlated with share prices and the relationship is very strong (R is positive and is much closer to 1). From C in the last table, we can conclude that on average, for every fluctuation in the exchange rates, the share prices of HDFC Company vary by a value of .155.

ICICI

REGRESSION

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
share prices	35.706571	5.5253788	45
exchange rates	52.339429	5.7382637	45

Correlations			
		share prices	exchange rates
Pearson Correlation	share prices	1.000	.512
	exchange rates	.512	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	share prices	.	.001
	exchange rates	.001	.
N	share prices	45	45
	exchange rates	45	45

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Variables Entered/Removed ^a	
Variables Entered	
exchange rates ^b	
a. Dependent Variable: share prices	
b. All requested variables entered.	

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.512 ^a	.262	.240	4.8172499
a. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	272.219	1	272.219	11.731	.010 ^b
	Residual	765.795	43	23.206		
	Total	1038.014	44			
a. Dependent Variable: share prices						
b. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates						

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	61.515	7.579		8.116	.000
	exchange rates	.493	.144	.512	3.425	.010

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

From B in the fifth table, since the p-value is 0.010, the relationship between exchange rates and share prices is significant. From A in the fourth table, the correlation coefficient, R, is 0.512. Therefore, we can conclude that exchange rates are positively correlated with share prices and the relationship is very strong (R is positive and is much closer to 1). From C in the last table, we can conclude that on average, for every fluctuation in the exchange rates, the share prices of ICICI Company vary by a value of .493.

INFOSYS

REGRESSION

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
share prices	50.006571	7.7242342	45
exchange rates	52.339429	5.7382637	45

Correlations

		share prices	exchange rates
Pearson Correlation	share prices	1.000	.567
	exchange rates	.567	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	share prices	.	.000
	exchange rates	.000	.
N	share prices	45	45
	exchange rates	45	45

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	exchange rates ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.567 ^a	.322	.301	6.4567277

a. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	652.821	1	652.821	15.659	.000 ^b
Residual	1375.748	43	41.689		
Total	2028.569	44			

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

b. Predictors: (Constant), exchange rates

COEFFICIENTS^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	89.974	10.159		8.857	.000
exchange rates	.764	.193	.567	3.957	.000

a. Dependent Variable: share prices

From B in the fifth table, since the p-value is 0, the relationship between exchange rates and share prices is significant. From A in the fourth table, the correlation coefficient, R, is 0.567. Therefore, we can conclude that exchange rates are positively correlated with share prices and the relationship is very strong (R is positive and is much closer to 1). From C in the last table, we can conclude that on average, for every fluctuation in the exchange rates, the share prices of Infosys Company vary by a value of .764.

5. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study determined that there is a significant relation between the exchange rate fluctuations and stock markets. The primary purpose of this study was to find whether there is an impact of exchange rate fluctuations on the share prices of the National Stock Exchange. A few Top Indian MNCs listed under National Stock Exchange were taken into consideration along with their share prices and also the fluctuations in the exchange rate of US Dollar. Under Regression analysis it was found out that both the share prices and the exchange rates fluctuations are positively correlated with each other. I find that appreciating exchange rate boosts the stock market.

Firstly, it is to be determined whether the US should pursue a policy of strengthening the USD. An appreciation of the US Dollar will cause the returns to rise and vice versa. The positive relationship that I found suggests that such a policy would also be beneficial for the stock market. Secondly, multinational companies interested in exchange rate forecasting may consider the stock market as a forecasting indicator—when it rises, the currency is expected to depreciate. Finally, the relationship I find proves to be extremely beneficial in a case of financial crisis. Thus for a stable stock market, exchange rate has to be maintained in a favorably territory.

REFERENCES

- Ajayi, R. A. and Mougoue, M., 1996. On the Dynamic Relation between Stock Prices and Exchange Rates. *The Journal of Financial Research* 19: 193-207
- Gavin, M., 1989. The Stock Market and Exchange Rate Dynamics, *Journal of International Money and Finance* 8:181-200.
- Bahmani-Oskooee, R. and Sohrabian, A. (1992). Stock prices and the effective exchange rate of the dollar. *Applied Economics*, Vol. 24 (4), pp. 193-207
- Bremer, M. and Hiraki, T. (1999). Volume and individual security returns on the Tokyo Stock Exchange, *Pacific Basin Finance Journal*, Vol. 7 (3-4) pp. 351 –370.
- Lin, C. (2012). The comovement between exchange rates and stock prices in the Asian emerging markets, *International Review of Economics and Finance*, Vol. 22 (1), pp. 161 – 172.